

Social and Cultural Capital in Patthana Soi Ranongklang Community, Dusit District, Bangkok

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I. INTRODUCTION

Abstract—This research aimed to study the characteristics of a community in the social, economic and cultural context. This research used interviews and surveys of the members in the Patthana Soi Ranongklang community, Dusit District, Bangkok. The results are as follows: In terms of overall conditions and characteristics, the Patthana Soi Ranongklang community is located on the property of the Treasury Department. 50 years ago, the location of this community consisted of paddy fields with limited convenience in terms of transportation. Rama V Road was only a small narrow road accessed only by three-wheelers there were no buses. The majority of community members moved in from Mak Khawan Rangsang Bridge. Thus, most community members were either workers or government officials as they were renters not the owners of the land. Therefore, there were no primary occupations within the 7 acres of this community. The development of the community started in 1981. At present, the community is continuously being developed and modernization is rapidly flowing in. One of the reasons was because the main roads were widened, especially Rama V Road that allows more convenient transportation, leading to heightened citizens' convenience. In terms of the economy and society, Rama V Road causes the research to find out the development and expansion of change in the conditions of the area and buildings. Some buildings were improved and changed along the time, as well as the development of new facilities that caused the community members to continually become more materialistic. In the community, it has well organized and managed jobs to each part of community members, and areas were improved to allow the new buildings and apartments. The trend of jobs became more varied, in terms of both jobs at home, such as workers, merchandizing and small own businesses, and the community jobs outside, which became much more convenient to car drivers as they got used to the narrow roads inside the community. The location of the community next to Rama V Road also allows assistance from government agencies to reach the community with ease. Moreover, the welfare of the community was well taken care of by the community committee. In terms of education, the research found that there are two schools: Wat Pracharabuedham School and Wat Noi Noppakun School that are providing education within the community. The majority in the community have received Bachelor degrees. In areas of culture, the research found that the culture, traditions and beliefs of people in the community were mainly transferred from the old community: the majorities are Buddhists, so especially beliefs in Buddhism; the main reason for this is because the old community was situated near Wat Makut Kasattriyaram. Therefore, the community members have always had Buddhist temples as the centre of the community. Later years, more citizens moved along culture in and bring traditions and beliefs with them. The community members also took part in building a Dharma hall named Wat Duang Jai which is 72 year old.

Keywords—Social Capital, Patthana Soi Ranongklang community, Way of Life.

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THE Patthana Soi Ranongklang community is a crowded urban community, in which the majority of the community have to work for a living. It's located on Rama V road and its social welfare is accounted by the Dusit district office. The Dusit district has its name from the royal pavilion of king Rama IV in 1898, when he spent his own money to buy this property. This district has its border adjoined by to: in the north next to Bangsue canal and Prempracha canal; in the south next to Pranakorn district and Pom Prab Sattru Phai District; in the east next to Phayathai and Ratchadevi district; and in the west next to Chaophraya River. The communities in Dusit district are melting pot culture but they can live together without cultural problem. The area of the Patthana Soi Ranongklang community, which is state property land, is about 2,800 sq. meters and has populations of 1,250 people including 195 families and 122 households. [1]

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To study the social, economic, political and cultural life of the Patthana Soi Ranongklang community, Dusit district Bangkok.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was processed closely by the interviews with community stakeholders such as the leaders and the elderly of the community and by using in-depth interviews about traditions, language, literature, art, archaeology, music and recreation. Data was collected from a survey of residents in the community, observation of everyday activities and the participation in the activities people who is willing to cooperate in the survey. The interview was used to obtain information on the culture by interviewing a total of at least 30 people. The data was analyzed by using content analysis and document research. In the analysis documents, investigators must take into account the context by presenting the results in a manner described in the narrative.

IV. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Patthana Soi Ranongklang community, one of 44 communities in Dusit district, is a crowded urban community which has 2 housing styles: the first is the house whose base made of brick and mortar and its upper floor made of wood; and the second is 2-story commercial building. The community has leaders and their committees to manage many groups of facilities and activities (saving, sports, seniors, housewife, public health etc.). Most people in the community

are Buddhist and there is a local temple called "Wat Duangjai 72 Pansa" which is the center of religious activities for the offices and community events. This community has 7 acres by the majority Buddhists. Community space is in the land of the Treasury Department and which details the social, economic and cultural life of the community development Soi Ranongklang the community center is a community development. Which provides for the establishment of a community or a community leader for over 20 years and that is a strong community. There are community memberships that indeed arranged by the community board, savings group, sport group, Elderly education group, the cremation Act help group and volunteer group are the leaders in community development activities. To enhance the quality of life for the better, tradition as a joint activity is provided for the people in the New Year. Every year since B.E.2509, we are working and soul of the community the community access will be through Rama Vand a sign indicates clearly the community Soi Ranongklang, the concrete 2-lane named Ranongklang lane 3 lanes each lane can go through to Soi Ranong 1 and Soi Ranong II. This community cannot have two-way front mouth of the community and sides of the community Ranong Road, but the community center is a stalemate. The community can be accessed by a bus. The appearance of the house is very diverse. But there are 2 types of the most striking differences: 1) a house with wood and cement gate 2, 2) a house with wood and cement layer 2 (a gated) houses. The majority of the community houses are cement houses with 2 stories for residential purpose only, no gated clearly. Within the cities, there are many communities. Many of the buildings have improved significantly as funds of each family. However, it is also reflected in the past approximately 50 years ago, it was clearly the same. There is a second floor of the house which is built almost by wooden material. It has not been renovated or changed any more, but it looks a little bit newer by painting and repairing only. The inquiry found out that this will last about 50 years; many of the latter are born with the community. The floor is concrete, for living, dining, and watching television or working at the intersection, etc., which are mostly used materials such as cement and steel, mainly in construction.

The upper floor made of wood is functioned as bedroom. The basement is made of mortar functioned as living room, dining and kitchen.

The fence shows the better class of living and economy because they have more space and garage. The occupations of the members of these communities are various, such as laborer, company employee, government official, etc. But mostly they work outside the community, so the occupations that are left working inside the community are self-employed, low cost investment such as motorcycle-taxi, grocery stores, baby sitters, beauty salon. Their food is ordinary as most Thai people have. As a result of working outside the community, the traditional Thai culture left in the community is only on Songkran day and New Year day [2], which still have the traditional of inviting monks to perform the ceremonies and to bless for prosperity and luck of their families. [3]

Fig. 1 Wood and mortar house (no fence)

Fig. 2 Wood and mortar house (with fence)

Fig. 3 The community temple Ranonkhang 72

The way of life goes according to all forms of modern city life. The appearance of a new lifestyle that reflects the lifestyle of different people are clearly increasing more and more every day.

V.CONCLUSION

Patthana Soi Ranongklang community is an impoverished urban community within the context of social, economic and cultural life. The accommodations of the residents lack order and basic city planning that most cities are accustomed to. Within this urban lifestyle, it is common to see a single family

home with three generations under one roof, with the grandparents taking care of the children while the parents go to work to earn money in order to support the household. The economic realities of this lifestyle force the primary earners of the household to leave early and come back late in the night. This restricts the time parents can spend with their family by relegating bonding to national holidays. The majority of people in the community have to work, and as a result, if you go to this community during the day, you will only find the elderly and the children that they look after.

Fig. 4 Rama 5 Road near Community

Fig. 5 Road in Community temple Ranokhang 72

VI. DISCUSSION

Most people in the community are Buddhist and there is local temple called "Wat Duangjai 72 Pansa" that lacks a monk to perform religious functions and, as a result, if the members of the community want a small religious function, they need to invite a monk to perform activities. However, if it is a large religious function or particularly important day in the Buddhist calendar, they will make a trip to the nearby temple. [4]

Fig. 6 Community of Committee Participation Meeting

Fig. 7 Community Leader Interview

In regard to the working parents, they do not have time to teach their children the social etiquette or to give them a well-defined schedule that includes coming home at a certain time. As a result, children spend most of their time outside the house, socializing with friends (school, internet cafe, department store etc.) [5]. In conclusion, the combinations of these realities are eroding traditional Thai culture and they may be completely gone within one generation.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Young people of the community did not give priority to community development and lack cooperation in the public consciousness, because material prosperity made them move away from their families and communities. They are inconsiderate, unethical in their way of life, are more easily induced in a bad way to the acceptance of foreign culture without realizing the suitability of the culture of Thailand. All of these are clearly reflected in the young people in Soi Ranokklang community.

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